

SPECIES DIVERSITY OF EDIBLE DECAPODS CRUSTACEAN ACROSS THE FISH MARKET OF JABALPUR CITY, MADHYA PRADESH, CENTRAL INDIA

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Abstract

The Decapoda or decapods are an order of crustaceans within the class Malacostraca, including many familiar groups, including crabs, lobsters, crayfish, shrimp, and prawns. They are also commercially important to many economies as highly valued edible shellfish. They constitute one of the major sources of nutritious food for human beings. The domestic fish markets play a significant role in the livelihood of the rural and urban populations and people consumed variety species of prawns, lobster and crabs for their taste and protein requirements.

The present study was conducted to attempt to investigate the availability of marine and freshwater Decapods crustacean species diversity across Fish Market of Jabalpur city, Madhya Pradesh, India. The survey were conducted from 2022 to 2023 and collected different species of shrimps, prawns, lobsters and crabs from the different localities of Jabalpur Fish market. The variety of Decapods species brought in the Laboratory of Ichthyology of Zoological Survey of India, Central Zone Regional Centre, Jabalpur for identification. During the present investigation total 10 species of Crustacean belongs to 07 genera and 5 families were identified from the local fish market of Jabalpur. This is the first comprehensive study documenting the diversity of edible crustacean.

The information on the crustacean diversity of the market were collected and recorded from the different fish vendor's along with some question regarding common name of species, source of shell fish. The IUCN status, price of different shell fish in per kg and demand of the fishes was also discussed in the paper

Keywords: Decapods, Edible Crustacean, Fish Market, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh

Introduction

Madhya Pradesh is one of most important and landlocked state of the country and recognized as a tiger state and its large forest areas. Jabalpur is the one of the important city of Madhya Pradesh state. It has a wide network of rivers, streams, dams, ponds, reservoirs and lakes and found rich fishes and other aquatic fauna including shrimps, prawns, lobster and crabs diversity in the area. The important Narmada, Gour Rivers, Bargi, Khandari and Pariyat Reservoirs Rivers are flow from Jabalpur; make them rich and diverse fish and other aquatic fauna. The place is nationally and internationally renowned due to presence of Ordnance factories, several Government and State Research Institute and other several Governments and NGO offices. Jabalpur is situated central of India, thus different states are well connected by road and railways. Due to largest railway establishment in Jabalpur town, an influx of population is always here from different states. Therefore, their food preference and cultural practices is also different.

The Decapoda or decapods are an order of crustaceans within the class Malacostraca, including many familiar groups, including crabs, lobsters, crayfish, shrimp, and prawns. The prawn, crabs and lobster fauna inhabiting the marine, estuarine and freshwater ecosystems of India are diverse and fairly well known (Radhakrishnana *et al.*, 2012). They are of great importance to the ecological processes of aquatic environments acting at the different levels of the trophic chain as herbivores, predators, decomposers and prey for other groups. Most decapods are scavengers. Decapods are useful and appropriate models for many years of biological research and are also important to many economies as highly valued edible shellfish. Decapods crustaceans are possibly the most widely known invertebrates, due to the greatly cherished edibility, so they are highest commercial value. Despite of the large number of species, many are either too small or too dispersed to be exploited by humans that only around 1% of decapods are consumed as food (Conte *et al.*, 2021). Crustacean play an important role in the food web as they are an important link between benthic and pelagic organisms, fish and birds. Crustaceans are of great direct and indirect importance to humans, the larger crustaceans including shrimps, prawns, lobsters and crabs are use as food throughout the country and are therefore important to economies of local fishermen and fish vendors. Edible Crustaceans, such as Crab, Prawn, Cray fish and Lobster constitute one of the major sources of nutritious food for

human beings (Bugel *et al.*, 2001). Since seafood is recognized as a healthy food in terms of protein, unsaturated fatty acids and minerals, the demand for seafood in the global market is increasing. The shrimps and prawns have great economic value as they earn valuable foreign exchange (Shyam *et al.*, 2019).

Decapoda are highly diverse, with an estimated 17,500 extant species (Briones-Fourzán and Hendrickx (2022) of those morphotypes that are most easily identifiable as crustaceans, shrimps, crayfish, lobsters, hermit crabs, and crabs (Alvarez *et al.*, 2014). Although decapods include marine, freshwater and semiterrestrial species, the vast majority of species in this group are marine species (Anger, 2001).

In India as many as 437 species of shrimps and prawns (Radhakrishnana *et al.*, 2011) and 705 species of brachyuran crab (Venkatarama and Wafar, 2005) have been recorded previously, but due to inclusion of new species/new records discovered time to time by various scientists across the country from the freshwater and marine water of India. The species of shrimps, prawns and crabs are increasing every year, Valarmathi (2017) has reported 118 species of freshwater prawns and Pati and Thackray (2018) reported 122 species of freshwater crabs have been documented from India. In marine water, India is known to have 939 species of marine brachyuran crabs in 375 genera of 63 families (Pati, 2022). The Indian decapods crustaceans reveal that 117 species of prawns inhabit the marine areas which fall under the domain of commercial fishing and the number of penaeoid species now found in Indian waters is 122, which forms 34.9% of the world species showing high diversity of species. The fish market, where the fish and fisheries (other than fishes) are available to consumers at the right time and in the right place. The variety of fish and fisheries are available to sell for the consumers in the fish market and play a crucial role in economy and livelihood of the peoples from the urban and rural areas of the country (Sathiadhas *et al.*, 2012; Sit *et al.*, 2021).

There is no published information on edible Decapods diversity of fish market of Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh except Paunikar and Das (2023) investigated edible freshwater fish diversity of Jabalpur fish market, recently. The present paper gives the preliminary list of edible decapods crustacean diversity across the Jabalpur Fish market, Madhya Pradesh.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in different fish markets within Jabalpur city from 2022 to 2023. The fish market areas were regularly surveyed for

crustacean shrimps, prawns, lobsters and crabs species supply on the day and others marketing relation information were collected. The different species of decapods like shrimps, prawns, lobsters and crabs species were collected through during survey period with the help of observation of crustacean available in the market. The variety of Decapods specimens brought to the laboratory of Zoological Survey of India, Central Zone Regional Centre, Jabalpur for further identification. The specimens were examined for various morphological characters for identification. The collected sample of representative decapod crustacean fauna were identified up to species level using standard references. All the specimens of prawn were identified following FAO sheets (1984), Jayachandran (2001) and by consulting other relevant literatures

The different characters were taken for species identification and the identified samples were preserved in 10% formalin. The photographs were taken after and some questionnaire and interview taken to the fish vendors.

Result and Discussion

The systematic list of different species of decapod crustaceans from Jabalpur fish market, Madhya Pradesh, with note on families, species diversity, common names, IUCN status, rates in Kg and demand pattern is provided in Table 1. A total of 10 species, 7 genera belonging to 5 families of edible decapods (Lobster, Prawns and Crabs) were recorded from the fish market of Jabalpur. Among these, one Lobster species with one genus under one family, four Prawn species with two genera under two families, four Crabs species with three genera under two families were identified from the study area. The most diverse family was Penaeidae and Portunidae with three species and with three genera followed by family Palaemonidae with two species and two genera. The families Palinuridae and Gecarcinucidae were with one species one genera (Table 1, Fig.1).

The survey also indicated that the all 10 species of different families and genera of decapods were high or moderate demand in the fish market of Jabalpur. The rates of different species of decapods are range between in Rs. 300 to 850/ kg. The marine lobster *Panulirus polyphagus* species price of the lobster is very high and demand of the lobster species are also high in Jabalpur market. The rate of different prawns species are range between Rs. 450 to 850 / kg. The rate of marine prawn *Penaeus monodon* is 650 to 850/ kg and freshwater prawn species *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* is 650 to 750/ kg. The price and demand of the all the prawn species have very high in the Jabalpur fish market. It was found that peoples of the different communities like to

consume all the available species of prawns in the Jabalpur Fish market. However, the rate of four species of crabs is between 300 to 450/kg and demand have moderate due to many peoples are not interest or unlike to consume as compared to other crustacean species such as Lobster and Prawns. The three species of crab *Portunus sanguinolentus*, *Portunus pelagicus* and *Charybdis feriata* are marine water species and *Barytelphusa cunicularis* are freshwater crab species. Portunid crabs are one of the good fishery resources of Southeast Asian seas, which includes swimming crab, three spot crab (*P. sanguinolentus*) and blue swimming (*P. pelagicus*) are highly commercial value along with the mud crab. In Indian coast fifteen edible crabs are commonly available (Sathiyar and Valarmathi, 2018). These species of crabs are regularly found in the fish market of Jabalpur, peoples consume its due to their distinct taste, medicinal properties, and aboriginal faith in crab meat.

The price of the various species of lobster, prawns and crabs are depends upon the production/catch, supply, availability and demand from the peoples. According to market survey, the daily supply of freshwater and marine water decapods in Jabalpur fish markets relies on transport in ice box. It has been found that in the fish market about 100% of marine species of crustacean is supplied from different coastal areas of the states, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Maharashtra, and West Bengal. The freshwater crustacean is supplied from local sources rivers and reservoirs and from within states or different states. In the Jabalpur Fish market three to four big fish vendors are selling the marine and fresh water decapods and common freshwater prawn species, *Palaemon serratus* are selling by small fish vendors in and around the Jabalpur city. None of the species sold in the market comes under the Threatened category of the IUCN (International Union for Conservation of Nature) Red List, but, two species of prawns *Panulirus polyphagus*, *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* and one species of crab, *Barytelphusa cunicularis* are Least Concerned (LC) and 7 different species of decapods are Not Evaluated (NE) yet.

The Penaeidae, a family of marine crustacean in the suborder Dendrobranchiata, often referred to as penaeid shrimp or penaeid prawn and constitute the backbone of Indian seafood export industry as the major foreign exchange earner as well as source of livelihood for millions of fishermen in the country (Sathiyar and Valarmathi, 2018). In India, some studied on fish and fisheries diversity workout in the fish market of different parts of the country and play significant role of socioeconomic and livelihood of the people (Ghorai *et al.*, 2014; Sit *et al.*, 2021).

Table-1: List of Decapods crustacean diversity of Fish Market of Jabalpur city, Madhya Pradesh

Sl. No.	Family	Species	Common Name	IUCN Status	Rate/KG. (In Rs.)	Demand
1	Palinuridae	<i>Panulirus polyphagus</i> (Herbst, 1793)	Rock Lobster/ Spiney Lobster	LC	600-800/ kg	High
2	Palaemonidae	<i>Macrobrachium rosenbergii</i> (De Man, 1879)	River Prawn	LC	650-750/kg	High
3	Palaemonidae	<i>Palaemon serratus</i> (Pennant, 1777)	Common Prawn	NE	240-300/kg	High
4	Peneidae	<i>Penaeus merguensis</i> (De Man, 1888)	Banana Prawn	NE	450-550/kg	Moderate
5	Peneidae	<i>Penaeus indicus</i> (H. Milne Edwards, 1837)	Indian Prawn	NE	550-600/kg	High
6	Peneidae	<i>Penaeus monodon</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	Bagda Chingdi	NE	650-850/kg	High
7	Portunidae	<i>Portunus sanguinolentus</i> (Herbst, 1738)	Three spot swimming crab	NE	350-450/kg	Moderate
8	Portunidae	<i>Portunus pelagicus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Blue swimmer crab/sand crab	NE	350-450/kg	Moderate
9	Portunidae	<i>Charybdis feriata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Crucifix crab	NE	350-450/kg	Moderate
10	Gecarcinucidae	<i>Barytelphusa cunicularis</i> (Westwoodskyes, 1836)	Freshwater crab	LC	300-400/kg	Moderate

IUCN Status: Least Concerned (LC), Not Evaluated (NE)

Conclusion

The present investigation was carried out to explore the species diversity of Edible decapods crustacean in Fish Market of Jabalpur city to identify. A total of 10 species, 7 genera belonging to 5 families of edible decapods (Lobster, Prawns and Crabs) were recorded over 13 month study period from 2022 to 2023. The few species of Decapods were available in all the season in the fish market of Jabalpur. The present study revealed the commercial occurrences of freshwater and marine waters shrimps, prawns, lobsters and crabs in the fish market of Jabalpur city. They are particularly and other decapods are also the most significant sources of animal proteins for the human populations. The peoples of city are often used as these valuable food sources for the consumption.

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Panulirus polyphagus (Herbst, 1793)

Macrobrachium rosenbergii (de Man, 1879)

Penaeus merguensis (De Man, 1888)

Penaeus indicus H.Milne Edwards, 1837

Portunus sanguinotentus (Herbst, 1738)

Portunus pelagicus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Charybdis feriata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Barytelphusa cunicularis Westwoodskyes, 1836

Figure 1. Decapods species diversity in the Fish Market of Jabalpur City, MP.